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Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
UK Research
and Innovation

Student Undergraduate Level

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

Student Undergraduate Level Minimum Viable Skills Profile

Version 0.6 (August 2025)

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

The Skills4EOSC project has received funding from from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]. The information and views set out in this document are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission guarantees the accuracy of the information included in this document. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on the European Commission's behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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DOI link

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16923028>

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

It is recognized that Open Science skills should be immersed within formal education at its earliest stages. **Undergraduates are potential future researchers and open science practitioners.** By taking part in relevant open science training early, undergraduates become concerned citizens and better equipped to support open science.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Undergraduates addresses the minimum competencies and skills needed by undergraduate students at the completion of their degree program in Open Science (OS). The MVS profile for undergraduates considers that undergraduate students do not typically undertake extensive research projects. However, there are opportunities for undergraduates to interact with data and software whilst working on assignments. Therefore, this **MVS for Undergraduate Students is a general profile developed specifically in regard to data literacy knowledge**, as it serves as basis for relevant OS activities and knowledge of the FAIR principles.

For information related to basic skills for graduate students who are undertaking research activities, typically via dissertations and other assignments, see the MVS designed for Master's Students. For the basic skills and competencies needed, including postgraduate students (PhDs), please see the MVS for Early Career Researchers.

STUDENT - UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL

ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT:

- Research Performing Organisations (Universities)

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of why it is important for society that research and data is open and FAIR. • Ability to identify open science and FAIR principles, including relevant discipline or domain-specific information. • Foundational digital research skills, e.g. knowledge of the research life cycle; organizing and documenting. • Understand basic concepts of intellectual property and copyright and its importance in scientific work. • Ability to identify the principles of open licensing and the uses and implications of open licenses. • Know what is meant by research impact. Know the different types of impact indicators and how they work. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the importance of research visibility and know different ways to increase the visibility of research. • Ability to apply basic open science principles in the relevant parts of the research life cycle, such as: • Recognising reliable and trustworthy sources of data. • Evaluating the quality and reusability of data. • Recognising the different open access model for scientific publications. • Knowledge of how to share FAIR research data, code and software, including knowledge of how to use repositories. |
|--|---|

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration and interpersonal skills, being particularly able to engage in teamwork. • Written and verbal communication | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management • Problem solving • Critical thinking |
|--|---|

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

Contributes to data literacy activities that improves their OS knowledge and skills, including:

- Interpreting and critically evaluating data.
- Finding, selecting, accessing, and creating data sets.
- Ethically using, collecting and citing data.
- Understanding basic data types and formats.
- Communicating data with appropriate visualizations.
- Understanding how the data was collected.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

The undergraduate contributes to the following OS outcomes:

- Development of data literacy abilities.
- Acquisition of a baseline of generic foundational digital skills.
- Adoption, awareness and understanding of OS and FAIR principles.
- Adoption of responsible and ethical use of data.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: [European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology \(ESCO\)](#), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Synthesise research publications](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Manage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Plan](#); [Organise information, objects, and resources](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Show commitment](#); [Work in teams](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Address an audience](#); [Report facts](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Manage time](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology and engineering](#).

ResearchComp: [Problem solving](#); [Creativity](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Data quality assessment](#); [Open access publishing](#).

CSCCE: [Speaking and presenting](#).

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